

XMM-LSS at high resolution with LOFAR

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VIDEO Survey

4.5 deg² • Radio to X-ray data • Ideal to study galaxy evolution

XMM-LSS: Ancillary data

Band	Instrument	Reference
150 MHz, $\sim 10''$	LOFAR-NL	Hale et al., in prep.
150 MHz, $\sim 0.5''$	LOFAR-VLBI	Morabito et al., in prep.
240, 610 MHz	GMRT	Tasse et al. 2007
1.5 GHz	JVLA	Heywood et al., in prep.
50, 100, 160, 250, 350 μm	<i>Herschel</i> (HerMES)	Oliver et al. 2012
3.6, 4.5, 5.6, 8, 24, 70, 160 μm	<i>Spitzer</i> (SWIRE)	Lonsdale et al. 2003
3.6, 4.5 μm	<i>Spitzer</i> (SERVS)	Mauduit et al. 2012
Z, Y, J, H, K _s	VIDEO	Jarvis et al. 2013
u^* , g' , r' , i' , z'	CFHT	CFHT Legacy Survey
g , r , i , z , y	Subaru-HSC	Aihara et al. 2017
0.5-2keV	XMM-LSS	Pierre et al. 2004
0.5-2keV	XSERVS	Brandt et al. in prep

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Star formation

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Star formation Dust

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Star formation Dust Stellar populations

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Star formation Dust Stellar populations Accretion processes

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Star formation Dust Stellar populations Accretion processes

photometric (and spectroscopic) redshifts

High-quality redshifts

Jarvis et al. 2013

What can we see?

predictions done using SKADS

What can we see?

predictions done using SKADS

How high resolution will help

How high resolution will help

XMM-LSS at radio wavelengths

LOFAR Sources in XMM-LSS

LOFAR Sources in XMM-LSS

High resolution with LOFAR

High resolution with LOFAR

plus 9 more ...

High resolution with LOFAR

plus 9 more ... but there have been some computer issues

Summary

- Will be able to accurately classify and measure sizes of radio-loud population in XMM-LSS
- Comparison with cosmological simulations (Horizon-AGN) will inform on our theoretical understanding of radio-loud AGN
- Stay tuned ...